

Novel Raman fiber amplifier based high-power 589-nm guide star laser for large astronomical telescopes and optical ground stations

Simone Serafini^a, Eleonora De Muri^a, Martina Scrinzi^a, Daoping Wei^b, Ning Guo^b, Wallace Clements^b, and Roberto Biasi^c

^aLEOS s.r.l., via Portici 23, Rovereto, Italy

^bMPB Communications Inc., 147 Boul Hymus, Pointe-Claire, Canada

^cMicrogate s.r.l., via Waltraud Gebert Deeg 3e, Bolzano, Italy

ABSTRACT

Large telescopes typically require multiple (4 to 8) guide star laser sources with individual 589-nm CW powers in the 20 to 50-W range, with emission linewidths of ~ 5 MHz. The emission should contain not only the component resonant with the sodium D 2a line but also ~ 10 to 15% of the total power at the frequency of the D 2b “re-pumper” line. In addition, especially for the higher power lasers, the system should provide for frequency chirping of the emission to mitigate saturation of the return flux. We present a novel high-power laser guide star system which has been designed to reduce system complexity and cost while providing upwards of about 50 W and including generation of the D 2b line and a straight forward implementation of frequency chirping. The laser design is based on the amplification of the linearly-polarized CW output of an 1178-nm diode laser in a narrow-band polarization-maintaining (PM) Raman fiber amplifier (RFA) and the subsequent doubling of the RFA output to 589 nm. The narrow-line master oscillator laser diode is frequency stabilized to the D 2a sodium resonance via sub-Doppler spectroscopy of sodium vapor in a gas cell, eliminating the need for a costly wavemeter. D 2b single-sideband line generation is accomplished via a phase modulator+Mach Zehnder combination. The narrow-band RFA has an unprecedented maximum single-frequency output power of 130 W and is pumped at 1120 nm with 230 W from a fiber laser which can be located up to 30 m from the laserhead containing the RFA and the frequency doubler. The RFA output is then fed into a non-resonant frequency doubler with an innovative control of the relative phase between the fundamental and SHG fields. Conversion efficiencies are equivalent to those obtained with resonant cavity doublers but with the advantage of reduced complexity, especially for operation with frequency chirping.

Keywords: Laser Guide Star, Adaptive Optics, Optical Communication, Optical Ground Station, Raman Fiber Amplifier

1. INTRODUCTION

Laser Guide Star (LGS) systems are a key technology for modern astronomical observatories equipped with adaptive optics, enabling the correction of atmospheric turbulence and significantly improving the angular resolution of ground-based telescopes. In sodium LGS systems, laser radiation tuned to the sodium D₂ transition at 589 nm is used to excite the mesospheric sodium layer at an altitude of about 90 km, generating an artificial reference star for wavefront sensing [1]. An efficient excitation of the sodium layer requires the laser source to meet several specifications. Continuous-wave emission at 589 nm with output powers typically in the range of 20

Further author information: (Send correspondence to S.S)

S.S.: E-mail: s.serafini@leos-instruments.com

D.W.: E-mail: daoping.wei@mpbc.ca

Figure 1: Schematic view of the LGS system.

– 50 W or higher is necessary to obtain a sufficient return flux of spontaneously emitted photons. The spectral linewidth must be around 5 MHz at most to efficiently interact with the atomic transitions of sodium. Additional techniques are commonly employed to optimize the interaction, including repumping light to prevent atoms from accumulating in dark states and frequency chirping to mitigate spectral hole burning. At the same time, LGS systems must ensure reliable long-term operation, robustness, and simple maintenance, as they are typically installed at remote observatory sites and integrated directly on telescopes.

Several approaches have been explored for LGS systems, the earlier ones relying on dye lasers, which were complex to operate and dangerous, and solid-state sum-frequency generation systems, which were also complex and delicate. The actual state of the art consists of RFA-based high-power IR lasers with a resonant cavity for frequency doubling.

In this work we present an alternative RFA-based LGS system with a non-resonant SHG stage, a schematic sketch of it is shown in Figure 1. A fiber-coupled seed source followed by a 130 W, narrow-band, SBS-free Raman fiber amplifier reduces alignment sensitivity and improves the system robustness. A patented remote pumping configuration allows up to 30 m separation between the laser head and the electronics cabinet, which hosts the seed and pump lasers, reducing thermal load, weight, and volume on the telescope platform, where only the RFA and the frequency doubler are installed. Frequency stabilization is achieved through an atomic reference, removing the need for a wavemeter and keeping the thermal load of the spectroscopy unit below 10 W. Repumping is implemented using a single-sideband (SSB) scheme to avoid unnecessary power losses. The amplified infrared radiation is converted to 589 nm radiation through efficient non-resonant second-harmonic generation, reducing the risk of optical damage compared to resonant cavities, and making the system inherently ready for frequency chirping. The nonlinear conversion efficiency is enhanced through coherent magnification, which is achieved by tuning the phase between the fundamental and second-harmonic radiation.

2. RFA

The architecture of the remotely-pumped high-power RFA system is shown in Figure 2a. The pump fiber laser shares the same architecture [3] as the MPBC pump laser in the SodiumStar 20/2. It consists of two Yb-doped double-clad PM fiber lasers with emission wavelengths of 1064 nm and 1120 nm, respectively. In each of the Yb fiber lasers, Yb-doped double-clad PM fiber is cladding-pumped by two 915-nm multimode laser diodes (LDs) with each multimode pump LD having a nominal drive current of 12 A. The RFA has a traditional two-stage, counter-pumping, master oscillator power amplifier (MOPA) configuration and, with the enhanced remote pump delivery capability, it can be positioned up to 30 m from the 1064-nm and 1120-nm Yb fiber lasers which are housed in the fiber laser pump module (FLPM). As shown in Figure 2b, the 15-mW, polarized, narrow-linewidth (a few MHz typically) output of an 1178-nm seed laser is amplified up to 130 W in this two-stage RFA without reaching the stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) threshold, which is defined here as the RFA output power at which the backward SBS power reaches 1% of the RFA output power [2].

Figure 2: The remotely-pumped RFA.

Figure 3: The non-resonant SHG.

3. HIGH-POWER NON-RESONANT SHG

The generation of second-harmonic radiation in a single pass through a nonlinear crystal is subject to a trade-off between conversion efficiency and the power-handling capability of the crystal. In fact, high conversion efficiency can typically be achieved only with crystals that cannot sustain very high optical powers, which are necessary for LGS applications.

An alternative approach consists in implementing multiple passages of the infrared radiation through a nonlinear crystal capable of handling higher optical power. However, in such configurations the different dispersion of the IR and visible beams introduces a relative dephasing which progressively degrades the phase-matching condition, limiting the overall conversion efficiency. The solution we developed consists in introducing a controlled relative phase shift between the IR and SHG fields within a multi-pass configuration. This scheme allows compensation of the accumulated phase mismatch and preserves the constructive interference of the generated second-harmonic field at each passage through the nonlinear crystal, resulting in a coherent magnification of the nonlinear conversion process. The case of a two-pass configuration is shown in Figure 3a.

Using this approach, more than 60 W of output power at 589 nm was obtained, with an optical-to-optical efficiency exceeding 50% (Figure 3b). Further optimization of the optical architecture and thermal management is expected to improve the overall performance.

Characterizations of the beam quality and power stability were also performed. The measured wavefront error is as low as 13 nm rms, evaluated over the $1/e^2$ beam diameter and excluding tip, tilt, and defocus modes (Figure 4a). This parameter is particularly important for the performance of the adaptive optics loop. The measured intensity profile of the 589 nm laser beam is well fitted by a Gaussian distribution, with a calculated M^2 parameter of 1.02 (Figure 4b).

(a) Wavefront error of the visible high-power beam. (b) Beam shape of the high-power visible beam.

Figure 4: The visible beam quality.

Figure 5: Log of visible power.

Measuring the beam power over a time interval of a few hours, an rms stability of 0.8% was observed without applying any active control to the emitted power (Figure 5). This result already indicates good passive stability of the system and suggests that, after the implementation of an active amplitude stabilization loop, a stability better than 0.1% rms is expected.

4. SINGLE-SIDEBAND MODULATION

In order to have a sufficiently strong interaction of the high-power laser beam with the sodium layer, a blue-detuned repumping sideband is required to prevent the atoms from accumulating in dark states. This sideband is typically generated via phase modulation (PM), which however distributes optical power equally among two symmetrical sidebands, resulting in a significant fraction of the power being wasted in the undesired frequency component.

In our system, we overcome this issue by implementing a single-sideband (SSB) scheme, consisting of a cascaded amplitude modulation (AM) and phase modulation. The AM stage is based on a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM), whose operating point is actively stabilized via a DC bias to ensure long-term stability and reproducibility of the modulation conditions (Figure 6a). By appropriately tuning the relative phase between the AM and PM stages, it is possible to selectively suppress the red-detuned sideband, and thus avoid power loss (Figure 6b).

The SSB scheme is all-fibered, eliminating the risk of misalignment and ensuring stable operation. The electronics architecture allows on-the-fly tuning of the amplitude ratio between the main frequency and each of the sidebands, providing flexibility in optimizing the sideband suppression and overall efficiency.

5. SUB-DOPPLER HYPERFINE SODIUM SPECTROSCOPY

Instead of using a general purpose wavemeter for the frequency stabilization of the wavelength emission, we propose to include a spectroscopy unit in the electronic control cabinet. The thermal impact of the atomic sodium

(a) Modulation scheme for SSB repumping.

(b) Schematic interaction between amplitude and phase modulation when the optimum phase shift is set.

Figure 6: The SSB modulation for repumper.

gas cell was carefully taken into account to limit heat dispersion in the cabinet: a well-insulated chassis permits keeping the thermal load below 10 W. A saturated absorption spectroscopy scheme is implemented permitting one to resolve the hyperfine structure of the D2 line. A digital locking loop provides an emission stability better than 10 MHz. The mechanical design of the cell is also optimized to guarantee an easy and robust optical alignment.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

We report on the realization of a novel approach for generating 589-nm light for LGS based on a non-resonant frequency doubler. It is worth noting that this scheme, by its very nature, easily supports any frequency of the seed light which is in the bandwidth of the amplifier, thus making the implementation of frequency chirping for example much easier than in the resonant case. We plan to scale the system up to more than 75 W of visible power. We are also planning to test a fiber-delivery option for the visible light and a system for very fast amplitude switching with a high extinction ratio.

The proposed system is expected to reduce both cost and maintenance requirements through a simplification of the architecture and the extensive use of off-the-shelf components.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Activity performed under a contract with the Italian Space Agency (ASI). Activity funded by the European

Union - NextGenerationEU.

References

- [1] D. Calia et al. “The ESO transportable LGS Unit for measurements of the LGS photon return and other experiments”. In: vol. 8450. Sept. 2012, 84501R. DOI: [10.1117/12.926898](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.926898).
- [2] Vladimir Karpov, Daoping Wei, and Wallace R. L. Clements. *Pump laser architecture and remotely pumped Raman fiber amplifier laser guide star system for telescopes*. U.S. Patent 9,450,374 B2. Assignee: MPB Communications Inc. Sept. 2016.
- [3] D. Wei et al. “A remotely-pumped 130-W 1178-nm single-frequency linearly-polarized Raman fiber amplifier”. In: *Medical Imaging: Image Processing*. Ed. by M. H. Loew. Vol. 13097. Proc. SPIE. 2024, 130972J.